

Table 2. Mean values of breadthwise grain expansion for six generations and estimates of gene effects.^a TRRI, Aduthurai, India.

	TKM9/Pusa Basmati 1	ADT37/Pusa Basmati 1	ADT39/Pusa Basmati 1	IR50/Pusa Basmati 1	Improved White Ponni/Pusa Basmati 1
<i>Generation</i>					
P ₁	1.34 ± 0.007	1.38 ± 0.001	1.50 ± 0.005	1.57 ± 0.009	1.53 ± 0.010
P ₂	1.64 ± 0.012	1.69 ± 0.012	1.65 ± 0.013	1.64 ± 0.011	1.62 ± 0.012
F ₁	1.47 ± 0.009	1.43 ± 0.012	1.51 ± 0.010	1.60 ± 0.012	1.61 ± 0.009
F ₂	1.41 ± 0.007	1.48 ± 0.006	1.53 ± 0.007	1.59 ± 0.008	1.55 ± 0.007
BC ₁	1.41 ± 0.012	1.43 ± 0.008	1.49 ± 0.010	1.55 ± 0.008	1.54 ± 0.011
BC ₂	1.61 ± 0.013	1.61 ± 0.009	1.54 ± 0.010	1.63 ± 0.010	1.57 ± 0.009
<i>Parameter</i>					
m	1.08*±0.05	1.37*±0.04	1.62*±0.04	1.63*±0.04	1.56*±0.04
d	-0.15*±0.01	-0.15*±0.01	-0.08*±0.01	-0.03*±0.01	-0.05*±0.01
h	0.92*±0.12	0.35*±0.09	-0.27*±0.10	-0.11 ± 0.10	-0.10 ± 0.10
l	0.41*±0.04	0.16*±0.03	-0.04 ± 0.02	-0.02 ± 0.04	0.01 ± 0.04
j	-0.10*±0.04	-0.05 ± 0.03	0.03 ± 0.03	-0.08*±0.03	-0.02 ± 0.03
l	-0.53*±0.08	-0.30*±0.06	0.15*±0.07	0.09 ± 0.07	0.14*±0.07
<i>Effective factors</i>					
(d ²)/D	-	3.8	0.9	0.1	0.3
(h ²)/H	14.8	17.5	4.6	-	0.6

** = significant at the 5% level.

gene action is present, the pedigree breeding method is recommended. Dominance and epistatic interactions were also seen; selection in later

generations with one or two cycles of intermating selected segregants will result in lessening breadthwise grain expansion. ■

Inheritance of aroma in two rice crosses

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Two nonscented varieties, ADT38 and ADT39, were crossed with a scented variety, Badshahbhog, to study the inheritance of aroma in rice. The parents, F₁, and F₂ were grown in Nov 1992. For each cross, 2 g of leaf blades from 15 randomly selected parent and F₁ plants and 200 F₂ plants were soaked in

10 ml of 1.7% KOH solution in test tubes and evaluated for scent after 10 min by smelling the contents.

All F₁ plants were nonaromatic, indicating the recessive nature of the gene controlling aroma (see table). A 15 nonaromatic: 1 aromatic segregation occurred for F₂ plants in both crosses, suggesting that two recessive genes control aroma in Badshahbhog. Pedigree breeding with a larger population for F₂ selection is suggested for introducing scent into nonscented varieties. ■

Behavior of F₁ and F₂ populations with regard to inheritance of aroma.

Cross	Plants (no.)			χ ²	P
	Total	Nonaromatic	Aromatic		
F ₁					
ADT38/Badshahbhog	15	15	-	-	-
ADT39/Badshahbhog	15	15	-	-	-
F ₂					
ADT38/Badshahbhog	200	189	11	0.19	0.50-0.75
ADT39/Badshahbhog	200	190	10	0.53	0.25-0.50

Breeding methods

Evaluation of rice cytoplasmic male sterile lines for floral traits influencing outcrossing

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The success of hybrid rice technology depends as much on developing stable male sterility and restoration systems as on the amount of seed set on cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines by natural outcrossing. Rice is an autogamous crop; high outcrossing does not generally occur. Considerable outcrossing, however, has been reported in some wild species as a function of floral structure and biology. Environmental variation may influence the expression of these traits.

We evaluated 15 CMS lines for nine floral traits influencing outcrossing under two irrigated environments: 1991 dry season (DS) and 1991 wet season (WS). Five spikelets were randomly selected from the main panicle in each CMS line to record anther and stigma traits using stage and ocular micrometers. Anthesis duration was recorded as the time

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Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted.

Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.

Floral characters of CMS lines under two environments. Bangalore, India. 1991 DS and WS.

CMS line	Anther length (mm)		Anther breadth (mm)		Anther size (mm ²)		Stigma length (mm)		Stigma breadth (mm)		Stigma size (mm ²)		Style length (mm)		Pollen sterility (%)		Anthesis duration (min)	
	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS
V20 A	2.30	1.50	0.45	0.32	0.92	0.48	1.66	2.11	0.56	0.41	1.86	1.73	0.53	0.69	100.0	99.8	273	285
IR54752 A	2.21	1.83	0.65	0.40	1.46	0.73	1.52	1.69	0.60	0.43	1.82	1.45	0.84	0.86	98.8	100.0	238	250
IMA	2.19	1.63	0.64	0.33	1.40	0.54	1.33	1.62	0.43	0.37	1.14	1.20	0.83	0.65	2.8	37.0	250	205
Mangala A	1.97	2.13	0.42	0.41	0.83	0.87	1.25	1.46	0.42	0.33	1.05	0.96	0.55	0.79	4.5	13.8	205	195
Pushpa A	2.40	1.76	0.41	0.38	0.98	0.67	1.61	1.50	0.42	0.31	1.35	0.93	0.55	1.00	1.5	17.0	211	185
PMS1 A	1.90	1.78	0.39	0.35	0.74	0.62	1.36	1.46	0.43	0.31	1.17	0.91	0.63	0.63	100.0	69.0	256	260
PMS2 A	1.84	1.34	0.39	0.33	0.72	0.48	1.36	1.27	0.43	0.31	1.17	0.79	0.92	0.95	98.5	98.0	251	260
PMS3 A	1.98	1.74	0.37	0.30	0.74	0.52	1.50	1.33	0.55	0.33	1.65	0.88	0.69	0.66	100.0	100.0	284	290
PMS4 A	1.75	1.36	0.35	0.34	0.63	0.63	1.40	1.65	0.44	0.36	1.23	1.19	0.72	0.77	98.2	74.0	255	285
PMS5 A	2.02	1.73	0.34	0.38	0.69	0.66	1.36	1.45	0.44	0.33	1.20	0.96	0.76	0.71	96.5	100.0	251	260
PMS6 A	1.99	1.70	0.30	0.29	0.60	0.49	1.43	1.33	0.43	0.33	1.23	0.88	0.73	0.82	88.6	100.0	208	218
PMS7 A	2.37	1.91	0.43	0.33	1.01	0.63	1.55	1.45	0.54	0.33	1.67	0.96	0.72	0.90	98.0	99.2	256	260
PMS8 A	1.96	1.69	0.37	0.26	0.73	0.44	1.58	1.37	0.47	0.33	1.49	0.90	0.74	0.86	99.3	98.9	246	265
PMS9 A	2.23	1.89	0.45	0.33	1.00	0.62	1.58	1.35	0.53	0.37	1.67	0.97	0.80	0.61	99.0	100.0	285	290
PMS10 A	1.85	1.89	0.36	0.37	0.67	0.62	1.52	1.57	0.53	0.37	1.61	1.16	0.62	0.65	97.0	100.0	257	265
Mean	2.05	1.76	0.43	0.34	0.87	0.60	1.47	1.50	0.48	0.35	1.42	1.06	0.71	0.77	78.84	80.45	248.49	251.63
Range	0.64	0.79	0.35	0.15	0.86	0.43	0.41	0.84	0.18	0.12	0.81	0.94	0.39	0.39	98.5	86.2	80.0	105.0
CV (%)	9.39	10.52	23.68	12.12	29.94	18.78	8.20	13.82	13.00	10.43	19.17	23.81	16.26	16.18	49.96	39.68	9.88	13.76
SE (m)	0.05	0.05	0.025	0.011	0.067	0.03	0.03	0.054	0.028	0.009	0.07	0.07	0.03	0.03	10.17	8.22	6.34	8.93

between opening of the first spikelet in the main panicle in the morning and closing of all spikelets in that panicle.

Genotypes performed very differently under the two environments (see table). In general, the mean values for anther length, anther breadth, anther size, stigma breadth, and stigma size were greater in DS than in WS, while mean values for stigma length and pollen sterility were

greater in WS than in DS. No difference was observed between the environments for anthesis duration. Anthesis, however, started earlier (0900 h) in DS than in WS (1100 h).

Variability (indicated by range and coefficient of variation) for anther breadth, anther size, stigma breadth, and pollen sterility was higher in DS than in WS; for anther length, stigma length,

stigma size, style length, and anthesis duration, variability was higher in WS than in DS. Expression of floral traits influencing outcrossing was generally better in DS than in WS.

Results suggest that it is advantageous to produce hybrid rice seed during DS because more floral traits are better expressed than during WS. ■

Restorers and maintainers for MS 577 A and wild abortive cytoplasmic male sterility system

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Ninety-six rice genotypes were crossed with six cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines possessing cytoplasmic male sterility system of MS 577 A and 24 genotypes with four wild abortive (WA)-type CMS lines, resulting in 252 F₁s with 577 A cytoplasm and 39 F₁s with WA cytoplasm. Based on spikelet fertility of these hybrids, genotypes were classified as restorers (>80%), partial restorers

(10-80%), and maintainers (<10%).

None of the 96 genotypes completely restored the fertility of 577 A. IR36, IR13146-45, IET7191, Karna, Milyang 54, and Nucleoriza, however, were found to be partial restorers.

Of the 18 IRRI genotypes evaluated, 10 were identified as restorers for WA CMS lines (IR8, IR36, IR60, IR13146-45, IR15324-13, IR20226-24, IR21543-2-1-22, IR27280, IR22810-60, and IR31916-9), 6 as partial restorers, and 1 as a maintainer (IR21916-128). Among other genotypes, 3 were identified as restorers (Cornell culture, ARC11353, and RP101-3-129), 2 as partial restorers, and 1 as a maintainer (local variety CTH1). ■

Yield potential

Performance of anaerobically direct seeded rice plants in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam

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Most farmers in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam practice direct seeding. Improved rice cultivars are used, but they were selected for use in the transplanting system. Introducing cultivars suitable for direct seeding may benefit farmers. We conducted this study to identify desirable traits for high-yielding direct seeded rice.